

RESCHOOL project reaches the requirements of technical development based on pilot use-case

On 31 October 2023, the RESCHOOL project reached the milestone of the “*Requirements of technical development based on Pilot Use-Case*”. The milestone marks the completion and submission to the European Commission of two central reports – D1.2 Requirements of technical development based on Use-Cases and D1.3 Guidelines for pilot planning and impact assessment. The reports provide details about the plan for implementation and evaluation in the project and thereby are important steps towards the project aim: to lever energy communities as a formal way to aggregate active consumers and prosumers and empower them as relevant energy stakeholders.

The public D1.2 report elaborates the RESCHOOL objective as a set of 4 Business Use Cases (BUCs), from which a set of 12 High Level Use Cases (HLUCs) have been derived. The BUCs aim to identify interactions with stakeholders in the energy sector at business level. Six technical HLUCs focus on energy management challenges of communities. These HLUCs include self-sufficiency and collective generation, participation in flexibility programs including DSO interaction (e.g., congestion avoidance) or aggregated access to markets or energy communities composed by housing associations with multiple energy vectors. Six other HLUCs on socioeconomic and engagement tackle issues related to public-private collaboration, the use of serious games and gamification as engagement and participative strategies, intergenerational training and learning or adaptation of communities to changing contexts.

The non-public D1.3 report provides a roadmap and implementation plan for each pilot in Amsterdam, Athens, Girona, and Stockholm, including objectives, high level use cases, stakeholders and responsibilities, infrastructure and associated investments, KPIs, deviations, risks and activity planning.

About the RESCHOOL project

The EU funded RESCHOOL project aims to increase the active participation of communities in energy markets, enhancing and facilitating the management and trading of flexibility in cooperation with sectoral players. The project seeks to improve the way energy communities operate by enhancing the technology and behaviour of their users. This will help to make these communities more efficient and effective in their use of energy. You can stay up to date on the project’s most important news, communications and events by following the [website](#) and the project’s [LinkedIn](#) and [X/Twitter](#) pages.

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